

CELL MEDIATED IMMUNE RESPONSE IN CATTLE IMMUNIZED WITH RECOMBINANT BM95 AND WHOLE

EXTRACT ANTIGEN OF *Boophilus microplus*

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Abstract

Control of cattle ticks by immunological methods attaining a greater importance due to limited success achieved with chemicals and other methods. The present study was carried out to elicit a cell mediated immune response by using lymphocyte stimulation test in cross bred cattle against *Boophilus microplus* were divided into three groups of six animals in each. Groups were inoculated with Bm95 recombinant antigen and Local *B. microplus* larval whole extract antigens (BmWE_{Ag}) respectively except control one. All animals were challenged with 100 unfed larvae in-vitro rearing and maintenance of *B. microplus* on day 30, day 70 and 120 day post immunization (DPI). Lymphocyte Stimulation Indices (LSI) were recorded positive on day 60, day 90 and 120 DPI after second experimental infestation in Bm95 immunized cattle whereas day 40 and 60 DPI before second experimental challenge in BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated animals.

Key words: Bm95 recombinant antigen, *Boophilus microplus* whole extract antigen, Lymphocyte Stimulation Indices, Lymphocyte Stimulation Test and Cell Mediated Immune Response.

Introduction

Rhipicephalus (Boophilus) microplus is also known as tropical cattle ticks are the most common ectoparasites infesting cattle and other domestic ruminants in tropical and sub-tropical countries. They cause enormous economic losses to the dairy industry by way of consuming large quantity of blood and acting as the source of several viral, bacterial and protozoal diseases. These bovine ticks have been estimated to cause an annual weight loss of 0.7 kg/tick and also been found to spread serious protozoan diseases like Babesiosis and Anaplasmosis among cattle and buffaloes resulting in colossal amount of health and production losses. Therefore, several traditional control measures and devices have been applied to control tick infestation in animals. Among these, the integrated tick management strategies have been recommended to reduce the various effects of tick infestation in animals. A major component of integrated tick control method is the application of chemical acaricides. But the repeated use of acaricides has been observed that acaricides are expensive and have adverse effects such as a high incidence of resistance among tick populations (Graf *et al.*, 2004), as well as harmful effects on hosts, human beings. All these issues reinforce the need for developing alternative and effective methods of controlling tick infestations in animals.

Keeping these in view of the increasing concern about environmental safety human and animal health, tick antigens were developed globally (De La Fuente and Kocan, 2006) that induced immunological protection of cattle against natural tick infestations. In this way, various concealed tick gut antigens (Bm86, Bm91, Bm95 etc.) have been recognized and used (De La Fuente and Kocan, 2006; Nuttall *et al.*, 2006), in which Bm95 has shown good promise and has shown to induce protection even against Bm86-resistant *R. microplus* strain (De La Fuente *et al.*, 2003). In India, Considerable work has also been accomplished on the use of whole tick, larval, nymphal, midgut and salivary gland extracts of *B. microplus* ticks (Raman *et al.*, 2000). Keeping these in mind, the present study was planned to assess the Cell-Mediated Immune responses (CMI) and evaluate the efficacy of both Bm95 recombinant antigen and Local *B. microplus* larval whole extract antigen (BmWE_{Ag}) in cross bred cattle by measuring Lymphocyte Stimulation Test (LST) against in- vitro rearing *B. microplus* strain infestation in cross bred cattle.

Materials and Methods

In-vitro Rearing and maintenance of *B. microplus*: Local *B. microplus* strain ticks were collected from naturally infested cattle herds in and around Ranchi, Jharkhand, India. Engorged adult female ticks were reared in laboratory at a temperature 28 (± 1)°C and relative

humidity of 85 (± 5) %. After oviposition, the larvae were preserved in B.O.D. incubator used for conducting experiment.

Experimental animals: Eighteen healthy male cross bred cattle of about 2 years age having no previous exposure to ticks were selected from Instructional Bovine Farm, RVC, Kanke, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India.

Bm95 antigen: It is a concealed recombinant tick gut antigen was obtained from Indian Immunological Ltd., Hyderabad. As per the details provided by the supplier, the source of the antigen was *B. microplus* Argentinean strain A (Genbank accession no. AF150891.2).

Local BmWE_{Ag}: To prepare a soluble larval protein extract, one gram laboratory reared 7-8 day old unfed larvae of local *B. microplus* were thoroughly mixed with 1% Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate and finally sonicated in ice cold Phosphate Buffer Saline (Vanden *et al.*, 2003). After centrifugation, soluble protein concentration (Lowry *et al.*, 1951) mixed with Freund's complete adjuvant.

Experimental Immunization: Male cross bred Cattle were randomly divided into three groups of six animals in each. The schedule of immunization with both antigens has been presented in Table 1.

Experimental infestation: Cattle were experimentally infested with 100 unfed larvae of *B. microplus* ticks reared in laboratory on day 30, day 70 and 120 DPI. These larvae were released on both the ears (50+50) of each cattle and the ears were covered and tied with cloth ear bags (Fig. 1).

Isolation of peripheral blood lymphocyte: 5 ml of heparinized blood sample was collected from each cattle on day 0 and 20 days interval up to two months then monthly interval up to four months before and after immunization. The blood from each cattle was diluted in 10 ml of RPMI-1640 media (Rosewell Park Memorial Institute-1640) containing 5% fetal calf serum. 8 ml of diluted blood was carefully overlaid over 4 ml of lymphocyte separation fluid (HiSep LSM, HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai) in 15 ml centrifuge tube. The tubes were then centrifuged at 400g for 30 minutes.

White layer containing mononuclear cells at interface of plasma and lymphocyte separation fluid were collected with the help of pasture pipettes (Fig. no. 2). The resulting pellets were suspended in double volume of culture media at final concentration of 2 X 10⁶ lymphocytes per 100 µL of culture medium. Cell viability was checked by Trypan blue dye exclusion technique and cells were counted using haemocytometer as per standard procedure.

MTT Assay: Quantification of in vitro Lymphocyte Proliferation Assay (LPA) was performed by using 3-[4, 5 dimethylthiazole-2-4] 2, 5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT) dye (Sigma- Aldrich, U.K.) as per the method described by Mosmann (1983) with minor modifications.

180µl of cell suspension from each animal was dispensed in 9 wells of 96 well tissue culture plates (TPP, Switzerland). Then, 20µl of media containing mitogen (Con A @ 40µg/ml) was added in three wells.

Fig. 1: Cross-bred cattle experimentally infested with *B. microplus* larvae.

Table 1: Immunization schedule of cattle with Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag} immunogens.

Groups (No. of animals)	Nature of vaccine	Duration of immunization					
		Day of 1 st vaccination			Day of 2 nd vaccination		
		Day	Dose	Route	Day	Dose	Route
A (6)	Bm95	0	1ml (200µg+M.oil)	I/M	15 th	1ml (200µg+M.oil)	I/M
B (6)	BmWE _{Ag}	0	1ml (250µg +FCA)	I/M	15 th	1ml (250µg+ FCA)	I/M
C (6)	Unvaccinated	-	-	-	-	-	-

M. Oil = Montoid Oil

FCA = Freund's Complete Adjuvant

Fig. 2: Separation of white layer containing mononuclear cells. (A) From Bm95 vaccinated animal. (B) From BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated animal.

Correspondingly, 20 µl of media containing antigen (antigen @ 40 µg/ml) of RPMI-1640 media was added in three wells of the tissue culture plate. In the remaining three wells, 20 µl of serum-free RPMI was added which acted as control wells. The plate was then incubated at 37°C in 5% CO₂ incubator for 68 hrs. After incubation, 20µl of MTT dye (5mg/ ml of media) was added in each well. The tissue culture plate was again incubated at 37°C for 4 hrs in CO₂ incubator. After incubation, 100µl of supernatant was removed carefully from each well without disturbing the formazan precipitates. Then, 100 µl of MTT stop solution (10 ml DMSO + 300µl Triton X-100) was added to each well

and mixed to dissolve formazan precipitates completely. Optical density (OD) was measured in an ELISA reader (BioRaid, USA) at 540 nm.

Stimulation Index and Cut-off value: The results of lymphoproliferative response (LPR) were expressed as Stimulation Index (SI) using the formula:

$$SI = \frac{\text{Mean OD of test sample}}{\text{Mean OD of control sample}}$$

The criterion for positive lymphocyte proliferative assay was set as 33% increase in SI of vaccinated cattle as compared to control animals.

Statistical methods: Data was analyzed with Win STAT (2003) software system. The mean values of all the groups were compared by two-way analysis ANOVA (Snedecor *et al.*, 1994).

Results

The mean values of Lymphocyte Stimulation Indices against Bm 95 antigen were ranged from 0.654±0.007 on day 0 to 1.124±0.019 on 120

day post immunization (DPI) whereas 0.658±0.011 to 1.119±0.012 on 40 DPI against BmWE_{Ag}. Although, LPR was observed significantly (P<0.01) higher from 20 DPI in both the groups but a positive LPR (cut-off value) were recorded on 60, 90 and 120 DPI in Bm 95 immunized animals while 40 and 60 DPI in BmWE_{Ag} immunized animals (Table 2).

Table 2: Lymphocyte Stimulation Index (LSI) against antigens in cattle on different days before and after vaccination (mean ± SE).

Groups (No. of animals)		A (6)	B (6)	C (6)
Nature of vaccine		Bm95	BmWE _{Ag}	Unvaccinated
Before vaccination	0 DAY	0.654±0.007 ^a	0.658±0.011 ^a	0.656±0.016 ^a
Post vaccination	20 th day	^B 0.771±0.008 ^b	^B 0.776±0.023 ^b	^A 0.657±0.013 ^a
	40 th day	^B 0.917±0.008 ^c	^C 1.119±0.012 ^f	^A 0.710±0.014 ^b
First challenge on 35 th day	60 th day	^C 1.150±0.014 ^f	^B 1.006±0.006 ^e	^A 0.634±0.007 ^a
	90 th day	^C 1.222±0.035 ^g	^B 0.969±0.019 ^{de}	^A 0.705±0.013 ^b
Second challenge on 70 th day	120 th day	^C 1.124±0.019 ^{ef}	^B 0.941±0.012 ^d	^A 0.719±0.020 ^b
	150 th day	^C 1.078±0.016 ^e	^B 0.860±0.033 ^c	^A 0.734±0.027 ^b
	180 th day	^B 1.015±0.018 ^d	^A 0.773±0.009 ^b	^A 0.747±0.017 ^b

Values having the same superscripts in column (small) and row (capital) did not differ significantly.

In case of mitogenic lymphoproliferative response, the maximum values of mitogen stimulation index for group A and B were observed 1.651±0.053 on 60 DPI and 1.613±0.093 on 40 DPI respectively. The cut-off values of LPR against Concanavalin A (ConA) for Bm 95 vaccinated animals were recorded on 60 and 90 DPI while 40 DPI for

BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated animals as shown in Table 3. The lymphocytes of control animals were not stimulated in the presence of antigen, mitogen and RPMI 1640 culture media and their LPR were lowest (below 1.282±0.007) than both the vaccinated group animals (Table-2 and 3).

Table 3: Lymphocyte mitogen stimulation index (LSI) against mitogen (Con A) in cattle on different days before and after vaccination (mean ± SE).

Groups (No. of animals)		A (6)	B (6)	C (6)
Nature of vaccine		Bm95	BmWE _{Ag}	Unvaccinated
Before vaccination	0 DAY	1.061±0.013 ^a	1.079±0.015 ^a	1.067±0.01 ^a
Post vaccination	20 th day	^B 1.097±0.012 ^a	^B 1.106±0.008 ^a	^A 1.036±0.004 ^a
	40 th day	^A 1.207±0.003 ^b	^B 1.613±0.093 ^c	^A 1.055±0.028 ^a
First challenge on 35 th day	60 th day	^C 1.651±0.053 ^c	^B 1.386±0.005 ^b	^A 1.056±0.007 ^a
	90 th day	^C 1.559±0.054 ^d	^B 1.313±0.094 ^b	^A 1.083±0.015 ^a
Second challenge on 70 th day	120 th day	^B 1.592±0.018 ^{de}	^A 1.303±0.056 ^b	^A 1.270±0.018 ^b
	150 th day	^B 1.542±0.029 ^d	^A 1.295±0.005 ^b	^A 1.277±0.049 ^b
	180 th day	^B 1.372±0.02 ^c	^A 1.292±0.004 ^b	^A 1.282±0.007 ^b

Values having the same superscripts in column (small) and row (capital) did not differ significantly.

Discussion

The antigenic specific responsiveness against both type of antigens (Bm 95 and BmWE_{Ag}) was lower as compared to mitogen (ConA) at the same time. The LPR of peripheral blood lymphocytes (PBL) of cattle immunized with Bm 95 recombinant antigen was significantly (P<0.01) higher than BmWE_{Ag} antigen and unimmunized cattle. Similar to the current study, LPR against Bm 95 antigen was lower than ConA, but a positive LPR of antigen was recorded only on day 50 and day 70 post immunization (Kumar *et al.*, 2009). Rose *et al.* (1999) also reported Lymphocyte Stimulation Indices (LSI) of all sheep immunized with TickGard^{Plus} and Bm86 co-administered with cytokines IL-1b or GM-CSF were low. In the present study, the LSI value of PBL was reduced at the end of second challenges in all the groups of animals. Similarly, Inocuma *et al.* (1993) demonstrated the percentage of T lymphocytes in PBL of tick-infested cattle was always less than in tick-free control animals, but this was only significant (P<0.05) at the end of the second infestation. This was observed in both lower and higher number of ticks infested cattle. The experimentally exposed *B. microplus* infested host had less LPR to in vitro lymphocyte stimulation with

phytohemagglutinin (PHA) than similar cells of unexposed animals, might be due to any immunosuppressive factor respond to direct effect on the reduction of lymphoproliferative response. Wikel and Osburn (1982) found that a significant reduction of LPR of PBL to PHA due to repeated low level infestation with *D. andersoni* (ten females and five males). Repugnant to these findings, Kavitha *et al.* (2015) demonstrated the antigen specific responsiveness of rabbits immunized with 35 kDa midgut antigen of *Rhipicephalus haemaphysaloides* was highly significant (P ≤ 0.01) compared to mitogen. The maximum LSI of 35 kDa midgut antigen was 2.47 on 49 DPI. Manohar and Banerjee (1992) observed antigen specific responsiveness in immunized rabbits *Hyalomma anatolicum anatolicum* was significant from 21 to 42 DPI. Similarly, a significantly higher LSI was observed from day 21 to 42 after first immunization in rabbit vaccinated with semi-engorged female *Hyalomma anatolicum anatolicum* whole tick extract antigen (Manohar and Banerjee 1992). Raman (2000) demonstrated the blastogenic response of peripheral blood lymphocytes to antigen of *Boophilus microplus* was elevated a peak on 42 DPI with methyl H thymidine whereas highly significant stimulation index maximum value of LSI

was also recorded on 42 DPI using MTT dye against purified antigen of *R. haemaphysaloides* (Aruljothi, 2003). In the present study, the results of LSI in Bm 95 (concealed) vaccinated cattle were significantly ($P < 0.01$) higher than BmWE_{Ag} (exposed) antigen may be due to immunosuppression induced by *B. microplus* salivary-gland factors was linked to factors other than PGE₂. Urioste *et al.* (1994) demonstrated *I. scapularis* tick saliva inhibits IL-2 production by T lymphocyte might be due to PGE₂. The low level of IL-2 in the tick saliva inhibited splenic T cell proliferation in response to stimulation with concanavalin A (ConA). Several co-workers published their reports regarding Lymphoproliferative response against exposed and concealed antigens of hard ticks but the role of cell mediated immunity against tick's infestation in cattle is not yet fully established.

The LPR was recorded positively on day 60, day 90 and day 120 post immunization up to the second experimental infestation in the cattle immunized with Bm 95 recombinant (concealed) antigen where day 40 and day 60 post immunization before second experimental challenge in BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated animals as compared to unvaccinated control animals.

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